

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF FATIGUE DAMAGE IN ORTHOTROPIC STEEL DECK UNDER MOVING VEHICLES

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ABSTRACT

Bridges are crucial parts of the infrastructure and play a key role in engineering fields by facilitating smooth, even traffic flow. Different types of bridges exist worldwide, each serving a distinct purpose and applying to different environmental conditions. Bridges lose their structural integrity over time and can sustain damage from various factors such as infrastructure issues and earthquakes. Bridge damage can have severe consequences, posing significant risks to infrastructure integrity, particularly fatigue damage, which results in sudden failure. Periodic inspection plays a vital role in identifying early signs of damage and extending structural integrity. Orthotropic steel decks (OSDs) are innovative and widely used structural elements whose distinct design facilitates efficient load distribution and reduces the bridge weight while ensuring superior durability and flexibility. Although many improvements in the design of the steel decks have been made, fatigue damage and cracking due to traffic loads remain essential issues. In this paper, an experimental investigation on a steel deck has been carried out to evaluate fatigue damage in the early stage. The U-rib is welded to the deck plate and diaphragm to prevent fracture during the tests. All the experimental procedures are according to the Australian Standards. The investigation involves an assessment of fatigue and stress distribution in structural details, along with applying various loads to determine the steel yield load. Furthermore, a thorough analysis is conducted on failure modes and crack patterns.

Keywords: orthotropic steel deck (OSD), fatigue damage, vehicle loading

1 INTRODUCTION

An orthotropic steel deck (OSD) is a system where a steel deck plate is stiffened by longitudinal ribs and transverse floor beams (or diaphragms). Many of the world's modern bridges use orthotropic steel plate systems for traffic load distribution in decks and compression stiffening of slender plate elements. The unique design of OSDs decreases overall bridge weight while increasing durability and flexibility. OSD damage can have severe consequences, posing significant risks to infrastructure integrity, particularly fatigue damage, which results in sudden failure. Aggarwal and Parameswaran (2015) studied the impact of overweight vehicles on the fatigue damage of a longitudinal girder of a steel-concrete bridge (1). Cui et al. (2018) investigated the fatigue reliability of deck-to-rib joints in OSD based on strain energy and stochastic traffic load. The findings revealed that welding residual stress had a significant adverse effect on fatigue resistance (2). Cui et al. (2020) developed a framework for predicting fatigue damage of OSD in cable-stayed bridges. The results showed that precise evaluation of fatigue damage necessitates consideration of road surface conditions and pavement temperature (3). Deng et al. (2021) studied the fatigue performance of composite OSD under moving loads utilising ultra-high-performance concrete (UHPC) (4). Based on finite element analysis, Zou et al. (2022) investigated the impact of stress reversals on the fatigue assessment of conventional OSD and a lightweight composite deck (5). Feng et al. (2023) utilised coupled train-

track-bridge analysis and the hot-spot stress approach to study the dynamic reactions and fatigue evaluation of OSD in railway bridges. This paper serves as a guide for designing and assessing OSD in railway bridges (6). A limited number of studies have been conducted on fatigue damage detection in orthotropic steel decks under cyclic loading, and the practical problems highlight the need for additional research and development in the field of bridge health monitoring. Therefore, the research presented herein focuses on vehicle-induced fatigue damage identification in OSDs.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Main test specimens

The primary test includes a repeated vertical load test. *Fig. 1* illustrates the proposed steel deck with a 15-mm-thick steel deck plate. This test is simulated using an actuator and a spreader beam. The actuator is mounted on the spreader beam, which distributes the loads through the deck to imitate traffic loads. The Australian Standard AS 5100.2-2017 (7) specifies 3.2 m as the standard design lane for road traffic. Due to resource constraints, all dimensions are assumed to be four times smaller than their actual values to perform a simple test. The U-rib is welded to the deck plate to prevent melt-through while acting as a stiffener to increase the moment of inertia.

Fig. 1. Proposed steel deck

2.2 Properties of specimens

According to the Standards AS/NZS 3678:2016 (8) and AS/NZS 3679.1:2016 (9), the properties of the specimens are shown in *Table 1*, *Table 2*, and *Table 3*.

Table 1. Properties of steel

Material	Steel grade	Thickness (mm)	Yield stress (MPa)	Tensile stress (MPa)	Modulus of elasticity (E) (MPa)	Shear modulus of elasticity (G) (MPa)	Poisson's ratio (ν)
AS4100	300	15	310	430	200×10^3	80×10^3	0.25

Table 2. Properties of the U-rib

Material	Steel grade	Thickness (mm)	Top width (mm)	Bottom width (mm)	Height (mm)
AS4100	300	10	340	180	260

Table 3. Properties of universal I-beam (460 UB 82.1 kg/m)

Thickness of flange (t) (mm)	Thickness of web (t) (mm)	Yield stress of web (MPa)	Yield stress of flange (MPa)
16	9.9	360	340

2.3 Load

The loading procedure should be conducted according to the Australian Standard AS 5100.2-2017 (7). To ensure that sufficient loads are applied at all points along the road surface and that the bridge deck is adequate for standard heavy vehicles, the A160 axle load has been used. The A160 axle load, identical to the W80 wheel load, simulates a single heavy axle. As a result, it consists of two W80 wheel loads placed at 2 m intervals. The relevant standard specifies that an individual heavy axle shall be positioned laterally within a 3.2m standard design lane. Dimensional analysis is utilised to scale the applied load, which is given in Eq. (1) (10):

$$\lambda_F = \lambda_L^2 \times \lambda_E \quad (1)$$

Where λ_F is the force scale factor,

λ_L is the desired scale,

λ_E is the scale of the modulus of elasticity.

Therefore, the force scale factor is calculated as follows:

$$\lambda_F = \left(\frac{1}{4}\right)^2 \times 1 = \frac{1}{16} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 2 illustrates the A160 axle load procedure according to the Australian Standard and the loading pattern in this experiment.

Fig. 2. a) A160 axle load according to the Australian Standard (unit: m); b) A160 axle load in this experiment; c) Elevation view of A160 axle load

2.4 Fatigue testing

Fig. 3 depicts the fatigue testing setup. The load is applied via an actuator and then distributed across the deck using a spreader beam to replicate the traffic loads effectively. The maximum tensile stress and fatigue cracks are expected to appear in deck-to-rib joints and rib-to-diaphragm connections (11,12). The load used in the deck design consists of dead and live loads, which include the deck's self-weight and the A160 axle loads, respectively. Several strain gauges are placed in various locations, particularly near the deck-to-rib joints and rib-to-diaphragm connections, to capture stress at the hot spot locations, as these are common locations for stress concentration.

Moreover, strain gauges should be placed at the points where the loads are directly applied to capture rapid changes in strain. The cyclic loading is stopped when fatigue cracks have appeared. The steel deck needs to be examined for visible damages, and stress-strain relationships should be analysed for fatigue evaluation.

It should be noted that Western Sydney University (WSU) Structural Lab imposes a maximum load capacity of 400 kN with a frequency of 2-3 Hz; therefore, the authors designed this experiment through finite element modelling (FEM) to fully align with the lab's requirements.

Fig. 3. Test setup for fatigue testing

2.5 Finite element modelling to design testing protocols

This section focuses on developing the initial numerical model using Abaqus software (Fig. 4). The weld is meshed using 8-node linear brick reduced integration solid elements. The deck and U-rib are meshed using 8-node linear brick reduced integration solid elements. The boundary conditions are defined in such a way that the cross sections at both end sides are constrained in the z -direction degrees of freedom, and the cross sections at both sides are constrained in the x -direction and y -direction degrees of freedom.

Fig. 4. Modelling of the deck in Abaqus software

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Evaluation of steel yield load

Different loads are applied on the deck using Abaqus software to determine the steel yield load. The maximum stress and deflection values obtained in response to escalating loads are shown in *Table 4*.

Table 4. Maximum stress and deflection values in response to the escalating loads

Load (kN)	10	12	15	25
Maximum stress (MPa)	225	265	310	310
Maximum deflection (mm)	0.89	1.13	1.49	2.76

As can be seen, steel reaches its yield stress under 15 kN. For a better perception, *Fig. 5* illustrates the maximum stress of the deck under escalating loads.

Fig. 5. Maximum stress in response to the escalating loads

In the early stage of loading, as stress (force per unit area) is applied to the steel specimen, it deforms elastically. This means the material returns to its original shape once the load is released, and the stress-strain relationship is linear. The material begins to deform permanently or plastically as the applied stress increases. The yield point is the point at which this transition occurs. The stress-strain curve continues to grow after yielding, indicating continued plastic deformation. This means the material deforms when under load but does not return to its original shape after the load is removed. *Fig. 6* shows the stress-strain curve for the steel.

Fig. 6. Stress-strain curve for the steel

Fig. 7 shows the maximum deflection of the deck under escalating loads. As observed, the maximum deflection rises with an increase in the applied load.

Fig. 7. Maximum deflection in response to the escalating loads

3.2 Stress distribution

Fig. 8 depicts the stress distribution along the deck's centreline under escalating loads. It should be noted that d and w represent the distance from the edge and the width of the deck, respectively, for dimensionless purposes. It is crucial to note that even simplified models can provide useful insights into complex structural behaviours. In this scenario, the single stiffener serves as a simplified representation for investigating fundamental aspects of shear lag and its effects on structural performance. The single-point loads are designed to be moveable along the deck plate, simulating the nature of traffic loads. By enabling these loads, the model can simulate varying load distributions and positions, allowing for a more in-depth analysis of how different configurations affect structural response and performance.

Fig. 8. Stress distribution under different loadings

It can be observed that as the applied load increases, the stress levels visibly rise. At the loading points, the deck experiences maximum stress. Deflection along the centreline of the deck under escalating loads is shown in Fig. 9. Similar to the stress distribution, the deflection rises with an increase in the applied load. Deflection refers to the displacement or deformation of a structural member under loads, and in this case, the figure depicts how the deck responds to increasing loads. This figure shows how the deflection of the deck changes with increasing loads, with higher loads leading to greater deflections. The peak values indicate areas where the deflection is maximum. Identifying these peak values can be crucial for understanding potential stress concentration and designing the structure.

Fig. 9. Deflection under different loadings

3.3 Failure mode

In this test, the deck fails due to the fatigue cracking that begins at the rib-to-deck welded joint and spreads to the deck plate. The deck is subjected to 15 kN, indicating the discreteness of the fatigue test results. Regarding failure mode, Fig. 10 depicts a root-deck crack propagation at failure.

Fig. 10. Observation of root-deck crack during the test

During the experiment, several cracks were created, indicating non-uniform loading distribution. Fatigue cracks initiated in the weld root and spread to the deck plate. The crack propagation can be achieved by measuring the distance between each crack. The progress of the fatigue crack growth during the test is obtained by combining it with the loading history. The crack growth tends to increase steadily in both length and depth directions. The fatigue crack entered the rapid propagation level after reaching a depth of 10 mm. At this stage, the fatigue crack grows faster, and the specimen is on the verge of failing.

3.4 Fatigue crack analysis

Under various stress cycles, the fatigue crack size in the crossbeam opening was measured. After 2 million cycles, noticeable cracks with a crack size of 10 mm were noticed on the surface of the crossbeam opening at the U-rib. After 3 million loading cycles, the crack propagation rate gradually slowed but continued to increase until the experiment was completed after 3.5 million loading cycles, at which point the crack length extended to 50 mm. *Fig. 11* depicts the crack size in the crossbeam opening under different loading cycles. The testing frequency was set at 1 Hz and was conducted at ambient temperature. The minimum and maximum loading forces were set to 15 kN and 100 kN, respectively.

Fig. 11. Crack length variation

4 CONCLUSION

This paper experimentally investigated the fatigue damage of OSDs in the early stage. Based on the performed analysis, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- A convenient and practical vehicle loading technique was presented to accurately capture the stress distribution of high-stress locations.
- The stress level and deflection rise with an increase in the applied load.
- The deck fails due to the fatigue cracking that begins at the rib-to-deck welded joint and spreads to the deck plate.
- Crack growth tends to increase steadily in both length and depth directions under loading cycles.
- The specimen's deflection data can be utilised as a signal for concluding the test.

Limited research has been conducted on the fatigue damage of OSD subjected to vehicle loading. Practical challenges highlight the necessity for additional research and development in the field of bridge health monitoring.

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